

Influence of water injection on the formation of CO emissions in oxyfuel combustion of low calorific gaseous fuels

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ABSTRACT

Oxyfuel combustion is a promising approach to apply carbon capture and thus counteract global warming. The pure oxygen used as an oxidizer is usually diluted with CO₂, H₂O or recirculated flue gas to moderate the combustion temperature, which influences the combustion characteristics like temperature distribution and CO formation. This paper deals with how the injection of liquid water in the combustion chamber affects the characteristics of MILD oxyfuel combustion of a low calorific natural gas/CO₂ mixture, which is supposed to represent biogas. Experimental tests are carried out on a 50 kW pilot plant, where the amount of recirculated flue gas and the water injection rate are varied in order to determine whether the influences can also be measured in the cold carbon-capture-ready flue gas. Moreover, CFD simulations of the combustion process with and without water injection are conducted to better understand the influence of water injection on the combustion characteristics. Results show that the injection of water leads to lower CO emissions, measurable in the cold flue gas. Furthermore, the reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$, which is mainly responsible for CO combustion, is shifted to the right side, indicating a promotion in CO burnout. In addition, it is found that water injection is an efficient way of controlling the combustion chamber temperature in oxyfuel combustion systems without causing significant temperature peaks or strong inhomogeneities in the temperature field.

1. Introduction

To limit global warming to 1.5 °C, IPCC scenarios [1] require long-term net CO₂ reductions. Alongside emission cuts, they rely on CO₂-negative solutions like AFOLU and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). As a rapid fossil CO₂ reduction is unlikely due to global growth and socio-economic goals [2], large-scale BECCS deployment becomes essential.

The oxyfuel process, which utilizes pure oxygen instead of air for fuel combustion, is one of the technologies for carbon capture. Due to the absence of atmospheric nitrogen, the flue gas is idealized to consist solely of the combustion products CO₂ and H₂O. Simple separation of the water vapor through condensation leads to a flue gas stream with a very high CO₂ content [3], which can then be captured more efficiently [4]. If a biogenic fuel such as biogas is utilized in this combustion process to provide thermal energy, and the captured CO₂ is permanently stored, this process can be classified as Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). However, an important challenge in oxyfuel

combustion is the removal of excess oxygen from the flue gas. A certain oxygen surplus is required to ensure complete burnout of the fuel, what leads to a residual O₂ concentration in the flue gas. The higher the concentration of residual oxygen or CO impurities in the flue gas, the more energy-intensive the subsequent CO₂ purification and conditioning process becomes. Until now, it has been criticized that the high energy input of 875–1200 kJ/(kg O₂) at the desired purity of 95–99.5 vol% [5], required to provide the necessary oxygen through air separation significantly reduces the overall efficiency of oxyfuel processes [6,7]. However, due to the rapidly growing global electrolysis capacity for producing green hydrogen [8] and the associated potential for utilizing surplus oxygen, a by-product of electrolysis, the oxyfuel process is increasingly attracting attention in the development of CO₂ capture technologies [9]. Given that the adiabatic flame temperature rises sharply during oxyfuel combustion with pure oxygen due to the lack of inert nitrogen, the oxidizer is typically a mixture of CO₂/O₂, H₂O/O₂, or CO₂/H₂O/O₂ [10,11]. In addition to diluting pure oxygen with inert media such as recirculated flue gas, pure CO₂, or water vapor, it is also

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feasible to inject liquid water directly into the combustion chamber to moderate the combustion temperature. The influence of CO₂ and H₂O in oxidizer mixtures on characteristics of oxyfuel combustion has been examined in several studies. Glarborg and Bentzen [12], for instance, investigated the influence of CO₂ concentrations in the oxyfuel combustion of methane both experimentally and numerically. They concluded that the increased CO₂ content results in significantly higher CO formation in the vicinity of the burner. This is attributed to the competition between CO₂ and O₂ for the H radicals, which causes the equilibrium reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$, primarily responsible for the oxidation of CO to CO₂, to shift to the left. However, according to their findings, issues with increased CO emissions during oxyfuel combustion are not anticipated. He et al. [13] investigated the characteristics and mechanisms of CO formation during the oxyfuel combustion of methane in O₂/CO₂ and O₂/H₂O atmospheres, both numerically and experimentally. They observed that in O₂/CO₂ atmospheres the presence of high CO₂ concentrations shifts the equilibrium reactions $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + \text{OH}$ and $\text{CH}_2(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$ strongly to the right, promoting CO formation. In O₂/H₂O atmospheres, the reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$, which largely governs CO burnout, is clearly shifted to the right. Biabani et al. [14] numerically investigated the influence of CO₂ and H₂O in the oxidizer on MILD oxyfuel combustion in a cylindrical combustion chamber. Different CO₂/H₂O dilutions were also considered. The concentrations of CO and OH in the combustion chamber increase with rising CO₂ proportions in oxy-mild combustion. When increasing the H₂O content while simultaneously reducing the CO₂ content in the oxidizer, lower CO and OH concentrations can be observed in the combustion chamber. Tu et al. [15] examined the influence of different oxidizer dilutions (N₂, CO₂, H₂O) on a Jet-in-Hot-Coflow (JHC) flame via simulation. It is demonstrated that the formation of OH radicals is inhibited in the case of CO₂ dilution due to the chemical influence of CO₂.

Abian et al. [16] investigated experimentally and through modelling the effect of different CO₂ and H₂O dilutions on the oxidation of CO in a flow reactor. It is noted that the reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ is primarily responsible for CO burnout. H₂O and CO₂ influence the pool of O/H radicals differently, which also affects CO burnout. In the case of CO₂ dilution, the oxidation of CO is inhibited as CO₂ increasingly reacts with H radicals and competes with the chain branching reaction $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{OH} + \text{O}$, which provides the necessary OH radicals. H₂O, on the other hand, promotes CO burnout, provided that excessive H₂O is not present. With high proportions of H₂O in the oxidizer, it is notable that H₂O serves as a very effective collision partner in the reaction $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{HO}_2 + \text{M}$. The resulting HO₂ molecules are degraded by OH radicals into the stable species H₂O and O₂, inhibiting overall CO burnout. The authors conclude that there is a complex interaction between CO and the H/O radical pool that either inhibits or promotes CO burnout, depending on the specific conditions of the mixture composition. Studies on flame stability, emissions, and combustion characteristics in MILD oxyfuel combustion with various dilutions (CO₂, N₂, H₂O) and oxygen concentrations in the oxidizer were conducted by Si et al. [11]. Both the experiments and CFD simulations showed that the lowest CO emissions are measured under H₂O dilution. CO emissions increase exponentially with H₂O dilution as the O₂ content in the oxidizer decreases.

Alves et al. [17] investigate the influence of oxidizer composition on CO emissions using a 6 kW MILD laboratory burner. The emission measurements indicate that CO emissions are significantly higher with CO₂ dilution than with N₂ dilution. Here, too, the explanation provided is that the high CO₂ content ensures that CO₂ reacts more readily with H radicals, shifting the balance toward $\text{CO} + \text{OH}$. The reduced availability of H radicals inhibits the reaction $\text{O}_2 + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{O} + \text{OH}$, thereby decreasing the formation of OH radicals and consequently the CO burning rate. However, the addition of varying proportions of H₂O to the oxidizer does not result in a noticeable reduction in CO emissions.

According to the current state of knowledge, it is recognized that oxyfuel combustion, especially at high CO₂ concentrations, results in

increased CO formation. However, it remains unclear from the literature whether this effect also leads to increased CO emissions in the cold, carbon capture-ready flue gas. When comparing emission data between air and oxyfuel combustion, care must be taken because the flue gas volume differs significantly between both modes. For this reason, CO emission values should be normalized (e.g., to the thermal input in mg/MJ) to allow for a meaningful comparison.

This paper investigates the MILD oxyfuel combustion of a CH₄/CO₂ mixture, which is intended to represent biogas. Our study differs in scope from others in the literature in the following ways: Firstly, the experimental investigations are conducted in a 50 kW pilot plant, which does not utilize cylinder gases to dilute the oxygen in the oxidizer, but instead employs flue gas recirculation, as would also be the case in practical applications. Secondly, rather than introducing water vapor into the oxidizer, liquid water is injected directly into the combustion chamber. This approach enhances the combustion process efficiency as the enthalpy of vaporization of the water is utilized to moderate the temperature in the combustion chamber. The objective of this work is to determine through experimental studies and simulations how water injection influences the combustion process and CO emissions of the oxyfuel combustion of biogas, and whether these effects can also be measured in the cold, carbon capture-ready flue gas.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the pilot plant's design and operational principles. Additionally, the methodology employed for conducting the experiments and simulations is explained. Section 3 presents experimental results, which include the measured CO emissions at varying residual oxygen concentrations in the flue gas under different recirculation rates and water injection rates. Subsequently, Section 4 describes the simulation results, showcasing the temperature and flow fields, as well as the distribution of key species and reaction rates. In Section 5, the findings from experiments and simulations are discussed, with the simulation results from Section 4 aiding in the interpretation of the experimental results presented in Section 3. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the paper and draws conclusions.

2. Material and methods

Fig. 1 illustrates the schematic layout of the pilot plant located at the Fraunhofer UMSICHT technical center in Sulzbach-Rosenberg (Bavaria, Germany), which is organized as follows: The fuel mixture is introduced in the desired ratio through a gas control line for natural gas (91 vol% CH₄, 6 vol% C₂H₄, 1.5 vol% CO₂, 1.5 vol% N₂) and CO₂ (gas quality 4.5) to the burner, which has a design power of 50 kW. The fuel mixture and the oxidizer, comprising a mixture of recirculated flue gas and pure oxygen (gas quality 3.5), are fed into the combustion chamber via the burner, which incorporates an internal heat exchanger that transfers heat from the hot flue gases leaving the combustion chamber to the oxidizer. The combustion reaction occurs there at atmospheric pressure. The flue gas subsequently exits the combustion chamber through the recuperative burner, whereby the oxidizer is preheated to approximately 600 °C. In the first step, the flue gas, leaving the burner at 700 °C, is cooled to 100 °C in a high-temperature heat exchanger. In the second step, the cooled flue gas is directed into the condenser, where it is sub-cooled to 20 °C to facilitate the separation of a significant portion of the water vapor present in the flue gas. The condensate is discharged via a siphon to prevent ambient air from entering the plant. A part of the dry flue gas (CO₂ > 95 vol%) is recirculated and oxygen is added upstream of the burner to form the oxidizer. The remaining portion is removed via a flue gas fan, which regulates the combustion chamber pressure. To moderate the temperature within the combustion chamber, liquid water is injected through three nozzles (Schlick Hollow Cone Nozzle Model 121V) using a dosing pump. The flue gas composition is measured in the dry flue gas after the condenser, as we want to examine whether effects of water injection on CO formation can also be measured in the cold, carbon capture-ready flue gas. Furthermore, the used FTIR Analyzer only works for a maximum H₂O content of 20 vol%. Additionally, we

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the pilot plant designed for the oxyfuel combustion of gaseous fuels at Fraunhofer UMSICHT.

wanted to minimize spectral interference of H₂O with the absorption bands of other species (e.g. CO) thereby improving the accuracy of the measurements of these components. Air may be utilized as an oxidizer to bring the system up to operating temperature.

Fig. 2 depicts the structure of the combustion chamber and the

burner. The burner used is a commercially available Rekurat CX 200 FLOX burner designed for recuperative operation. The fuel is introduced into the combustion chamber through a central circular nozzle. A ring-shaped nozzle is concentrically arranged around the fuel nozzle, allowing the oxidizer to flow into the combustion chamber separately

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the combustion chamber (left) and the burner (right).

from the fuel. The small cross-section of this nozzle results in a high momentum of the oxidizer, thereby ensuring the strong internal recirculation necessary for MILD combustion. The hot flue gas exits the combustion chamber through an external annular gap on the burner, which is separated from the oxidizer nozzle by a ceramic recuperator. Within the combustion chamber, the residence time is in the range of 1.5 s. The burner is vertically inserted into the cylindrical combustion chamber from above. The combustion chamber is 1032 mm in length and has an internal diameter of 400 mm. It is insulated with a 300 mm thick layer of ceramic fiber mats to minimize heat loss through the combustion chamber wall. At a height of 365 mm from the bottom, three openings are evenly distributed around the circumference of the combustion chamber, offset by 120°. The nozzle lances for direct water injection, which inject a hollow cone free jet of liquid water, are inserted through these openings. To avoid quenching the primary mixing and ignition zone near the burner head and to prevent thermal shock of the ceramic burner head, the water injection was placed in the lower area of the combustion chamber. The combustion chamber temperature is measured using a type N thermocouple and the measuring point is marked with a red circle in Fig. 2. During operation, it must not exceed 1200 °C due to the material properties of the burner. The opening for the thermocouple is located at a height of 665 mm above the combustion chamber bottom and is offset by 10° with respect to one of the three openings for water injection. The measuring point of the thermocouple is situated near the combustion chamber wall. Additionally, the combustion chamber has nine radial openings that allow the insertion of type N thermocouples with ceramic protection tubes. These thermocouples are used to measure the temperature distribution and, in this study, serve to validate the CFD simulation. The tips of the thermocouples are positioned such that they are located at the center of the combustion chamber along the symmetry axis. In Fig. 2, the positions of the thermocouple tips are indicated with red crosses.

The flue gas composition is analyzed using a Gasmeter CX 4000 FTIR analyzer (CO₂, H₂O, CO) and an M&C PMA30 paramagnetic analyzer (O₂). The measurement deviations of the analyzer are as follows: [CO₂] < 2 vol%, [H₂O] < 0.6 vol%, [CO] < 30 mg/m³, and [O₂] < 0.1 vol%.

2.1. Experimental methodology

Tables 1 and 2 provide an overview of the test conditions for the individual experiments. All experiments are conducted with a power of 40 kW. The fuel mixture (natural gas/CO₂) corresponds to the composition of purified biogas. In the first series of experiments, the amount of recirculated flue gas is increased by 10 m³/h at each test point, starting from 25 m³/h and reaching up to 65 m³/h. The CO₂ content in the dry flue gas is maintained above 95 vol%. To keep the combustion chamber temperature constant at 1050 °C at each test point, the amount of injected water is adjusted accordingly. At the beginning of each test point (V1.1 – V1.5), combustion is operated under slightly lean conditions ($\varphi = 0.8$, corresponding to about 2 vol% residual O₂ in the flue

Table 1
Summary of the operating parameters in the test series I.

Test series I						
Parameter	Unit	Value				
Trial code	–	V1.1	V1.2	V1.3	V1.4	V1.5
Fuel composition ^a	vol%	62.5 vol% Natural Gas, 37.5 vol% CO ₂				
Thermal power ^a	kW	40				
Flue gas recirculation	m ³ /h	25	35	45	55	65
Water injection	kg/h	19.5	16.0	12.6	9.1	5.8
Furnace temperature ^a	°C	1050				
Flue gas temperature ^b	°C	20				
Equivalence ratio	–	0.8–1				
O ₂ oxidizer content	vol%	27.6–33.6	21.3–26.0	17.3–21.1	14.7–17.8	12.6–15.4

^a Parameter is kept constant and is not changed.

^b Gas temperature after condensation.

Table 2
Summary of the operating conditions in the test series II.

Test series II			
Parameter	Unit	Value	
Trial code	–	V2.2.1	V2.2.2
Fuel composition ^a	vol%	62.5 vol% Natural Gas, 37.5 vol% CO ₂	
Thermal power ^a	kW	40	
Flue gas recirculation	m ³ /h	55	
Water injection	kg/h	12.9	6.2
Furnace temperature	°C	950	
Flue gas temperature ^b	°C	20	
Equivalence ratio	–	0.8–1	
O ₂ oxidizer content	vol%	14.7–17.8	

^a Parameter is kept constant and is not changed.

^b Gas temperature after condensation.

gas). The oxygen supply is then gradually reduced in small steps. After each adjustment the system is allowed to stabilize, and values of CO and residual O₂ are recorded. During this period, the FTIR analyzer records the flue gas composition (O₂ and CO) every 10 s, resulting in 30–60 individual measurements. This procedure is continued until the residual O₂ concentration in the flue gas drops below the detection limit (close to $\varphi = 1$). In this way, a series of data points of CO emissions versus residual oxygen content was obtained. In this work, the equivalence ratio is defined as

$$\Phi = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Fuel}}{\text{Oxygen}} \right)_{\text{actual}}}{\left(\frac{\text{Fuel}}{\text{Oxygen}} \right)_{\text{stoichiometric}}} \quad (1)$$

The duration for recording a test point is approximately 6 h.

In the second series of tests, two operating points are defined, each with a constant amount of recirculated flue gas. In contrast to the first series of tests, however, the amount of injected water is varied. To enable the recording of emissions at different oxygen surpluses, the procedure follows the same methodology as in the first test series, with the oxygen supply being reduced in very small increments, starting from ($\varphi = 0.8$) and reaching ($\varphi = 1$).

2.2. Methodology of the numerical model

Since the three lances for water injection are distributed at 120° around the circumference of the combustion chamber, and therefore do not present an axisymmetric problem, a three-dimensional (3D) computational domain is adopted. In preparation for this work, three different meshes were created: a coarse mesh (587,000 cells), a medium mesh (877,000 cells), and a fine mesh (1,038,000 cells) of the computational domain (i.e., the combustion chamber). A simulation was conducted without water injection. It was observed that there were only minor differences in velocity, temperature, and certain species distributions between the medium and fine meshes. Therefore, to save

computational time, the medium mesh with 877,000 cells is utilized. The multiblock structured mesh generated using ICEM contains approximately 877,000 cells, as depicted in Fig. 3. The commercial version of ANSYS Fluent 2022 R1 is employed to perform a steady-state computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation. Continuity, momentum, energy, radiation, and species transport equations are solved within the simulation framework. The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS) are utilized in conjunction with the standard $k-\epsilon$ model to resolve the additional turbulent stresses that come with the RANS equations [18]. Radiation is modeled using the discrete ordinates (DO) approach [18], while the weight-sum-grey-gas model (WSGG) estimates the grey gas absorption coefficients [19]. The turbulence-chemistry interaction is addressed using the PaSR combustion model [20], which is based on the Eddy Dissipation Concept (EDC) widely employed for simulating MILD combustion [21–25], where the volume fraction and time scale are computed based on local conditions. The detailed reaction mechanism utilized is the reduced mechanism DRM22 (based on GRI-Mech 1.2), comprising 24 species and 104 reactions. The kinetic parameters are therefore directly taken from the published mechanism without further modification. [26]. For modeling water injection, the Discrete Phase Model (DPM) is employed. The nozzles used exhibit a hollow cone-shaped spray pattern (30°) with a bore diameter of 0.45 mm and a droplet diameter of approximately 0.05 mm. All models are implemented using standard features available in Ansys Fluent 2022 R1.

Pressure-velocity coupling is resolved using the COUPLED algorithm. The least squares cell-based method is used for gradient approximation. A second-order scheme is applied for the discretization of pressure, while the second-order upwind method is utilized for the equations of momentum, species, and energy. The first-order upwind scheme is employed for the turbulent dissipation rate (ϵ), kinetic energy (k) and radiation equations. The applied sub-models and their main parameters are summarized in Table 3.

Boundary conditions are defined according to case V1.3 from Table 1. The simulation was executed once with (12.6 kg/h) and once without (0 kg/h) water injection. Inlet boundary conditions for fuel and oxidizer were set as mass flow, with the oxidizer composition configured

Table 3

Overview of the physical sub-models and core parameters applied in the CFD simulations.

Physical Process	Model/ Approach	Core parameters	Notes
Turbulence	Standard $k-\epsilon$ RANS	$C_\mu = 0.09$ $C_{1-\epsilon} = 1.44$ $C_{2-\epsilon} = 1.92$	Standard settings
Radiation	DO Model	Theta Divisions = 4 Phi Divisions = 4 Theta Pixels = 2 Phi Pixels = 2	Absorption coefficients from WSGG
Turbulence-Chemistry Interaction	EDC (PaSR Submodel)	$C_{mix} = \text{Dynamic}$	Chemkin-CFD Solver as Chemistry Solver
Chemical Kinetics	DRM22 Reduced Mechanism	24 Species, 104 Reactions	Based on GRI-Mech 1.2
Water Injection	Discrete Phase Model	Particle Type: Droplet Cone Type: Hollow Cone Number of Streams: 100 Evaporating Species: H_2O	Evaporation activated, Full coupling with gas phase

to provide an excess oxygen of $\phi = 0.98$. A pressure outlet is set as the boundary condition at the outlet. The boundary conditions for the combustion chamber walls are specified as stationary walls with no slip, assumed to be adiabatic, i.e., with a heat flux of zero, as the combustion chamber is well insulated with ceramic fiber mats. Measurements during the experiments showed a surface temperature of 31°C at an ambient temperature of 23°C and a combustion chamber temperature of 1050°C , which supports this assumption.

2.3. Model validation

To build confidence in the present modeling approach, the simulated

Fig. 3. Structured multigrid mesh used for the numerical simulation of the combustion process. Left: Axial section through the burner inlet. Right: 3D view of the combustion chamber with the inlets and outlet surfaces at the burner.

temperature along the central axis of the combustion chamber is compared with experimentally measured temperatures along this axis. In addition, the simulated temperature at the location of the combustion chamber temperature monitoring point (see Fig. 2) is compared with the corresponding measured value.

Furthermore, the measured flue gas composition (CO_2 , H_2O , CO) after the condenser is compared with the respective results from the CFD simulation. Since the CFD model provides the flue gas composition without accounting for condensation, i.e., directly at the flue gas outlet of the recuperative burner, the amount of water vapor remaining after cooling the gas to 20°C is calculated. Based on this, the CO_2 and CO concentrations are proportionally adjusted to enable a consistent comparison with the experimental data.

All experimental and simulated results used for validation are obtained under conditions of operating point V1.4, with an equivalence ratio of $\varphi = 0.98$.

Fig. 4 shows the temperature along the central axis of the combustion chamber as obtained from CFD simulations and experimental measurements. It is evident that the measured and simulated temperatures deviate near the burner. One explanation for this discrepancy lies in systematic measurement uncertainty due to the employed methodology. The thermocouple tip and its ceramic sheath are subject to heat conduction and radiation from the significantly hotter surrounding gas, leading to an overestimation of the measured temperature, particularly in regions where the actual gas temperature is lower. In the rear section of the combustion chamber, where this systematic measurement uncertainty is less pronounced, the measured and simulated temperatures are in very good agreement. An additional explanation for the discrepancies between the experimental measurements and the simulation results is that the simulated values are obtained precisely along the chamber axis, where temperature gradients are pronounced. Even a slight displacement of the thermocouples perpendicular to this axis can lead to significant variations in the measured temperature.

The comparison between the measured and CFD-predicted flue gas composition, shown in Fig. 5, demonstrates that the applied reaction mechanism is generally well-suited to represent the chemical processes occurring in the combustion chamber. This is particularly evident from the good agreement in the predicted and measured concentrations of CO_2 and H_2O , with deviations well within the expected experimental and numerical uncertainties. The prediction of CO , especially under near-stoichiometric conditions, is very challenging for CFD simulation. This is a known limitation of RANS CFD combined with reduced kinetic

schemes, because CO concentrations are very sensitive to local mixture fraction and radical pool (OH). Small deviations in mixing or reaction rates can therefore lead to significant overprediction of CO . Nevertheless, the comparison of CO levels in the flue gas shows that the simulated and measured values are of the same order of magnitude and thus in good agreement. Furthermore, the measured temperature near the combustion chamber wall is also in good agreement with the simulation results, with differences that can be attributed to typical uncertainties of thermocouple measurements and overprediction of the temperature through EDC.

3. Experimental results

The CO emissions resulting from combustion are diluted to varying degrees due to the differing quantities of recirculated flue gas at the respective operating points. To facilitate comparison of the CO emissions across the different operating points, they are not stated in mg/m^3 , but rather in relation to the thermal output and expressed in mg/MJ , as is common practice when reporting emission data for oxyfuel combustion systems [27]. Equation (2) shows the conversion of CO emissions from mg/m^3 (w_{CO}) to mg/MJ (q_{CO}). Here, \dot{V}_{FG} denotes the volumetric flow rate of the total flue gas in m^3/h , LHV is the lower heating value of the fuel in MJ/m^3 , and \dot{V}_F is the volumetric flow rate of the fuel in m^3/h .

$$q_{\text{CO}} = w_{\text{CO}} \cdot \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{FG}}}{\text{LHV} \cdot \dot{V}_F} \quad (2)$$

In Figs. 6 and 7, the measured CO emissions are assigned to the residual oxygen content in the flue gas prevailing at that moment in order to make a statement about how high the CO emissions are at the respective residual oxygen content.

3.1. CO emissions at different recirculation and water injection rates

Fig. 6 illustrates the CO emissions in mg/MJ relative to the residual oxygen content in the flue gas after the condenser. The five test points from test series I, as outlined in Table 1, are depicted. Each marker shown in Fig. 6 therefore represents the average CO emission corresponding to the respective residual O_2 content from many recorded flue gas composition measurements. In general, it can be observed that CO emissions increase as the residual oxygen content declines. This increase is much more pronounced at lower oxygen surpluses and is exponential.

Fig. 4. Temperatures along the centerline of the combustion chamber: experimentally measured values (green squares), simulated values at the measurement positions (red circles), and the continuous centerline temperature profile from CFD simulation (blue line). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Comparison of measured and calculated flue gas composition (CO₂, H₂O, CO) and temperature at the combustion chamber temperature monitoring point.

Fig. 6. Representation of the CO emissions over the residual oxygen content in the flue gas from test points V1.1 - V1.5 according to Table 1.

Fig. 7. Representation of the CO emissions over the residual oxygen content in the flue gas from test points V2.2.1 and V2.2.2 according to Table 2.

Due to the exponential increase, the ordinate (CO in mg/MJ) is shown on a logarithmic scale in Fig. 6. The CO emissions are highest at operating point V1.5, with the highest amount of recirculated flue gas and the lowest amount of injected water. A maximum value of 633 mg/MJ is measured at 0.04 vol% residual oxygen in the flue gas. At this oxygen content, the lowest amount of CO is 231 mg/MJ and was measured at test point V1.2.

To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the effects of varying quantities of recirculated flue gas (CO₂ > 95 vol%) and injected water, the scaling in Fig. 6 is adjusted to a slightly over-stoichiometric range between 0.6 and 2 vol% residual oxygen (bottom right) and to a near-stoichiometric range between 0 and 0.6 vol% residual oxygen (bottom left). In the slightly over-stoichiometric range between 0.6 and 2 vol% residual oxygen in the flue gas, CO emissions increase with higher quantities of recirculated flue gas and lower quantities of injected water. At test point V1.5, which features the highest rate of recirculated, CO₂-rich flue gas, CO emissions are consistently the highest. The same trend is also observable within the near-stoichiometric range between 0 and 0.6 vol% residual oxygen. However, it is noteworthy that the CO emissions at test point V1.1, which has the highest amount of injected water, are the lowest when sufficient oxygen is available. With 1.8 vol% residual oxygen in the flue gas, only 1.2 mg/MJ CO is detected. At approximately O₂ = 1 vol% residual oxygen, the CO emissions at test point V1.1 increase significantly, surpassing the CO emissions of

operating points V1.2 - V1.4 at comparable residual oxygen levels in the flue gas.

To avoid overloading the graphs in Fig. 6, error bars were not included for each data point. However, to clearly present the 95 % confidence interval CI₉₅, it is provided below in Table 4.

3.2. CO emissions with varying quantities of injected water and constant flue gas recirculation

To illustrate the influence of water injection on CO emission levels, Fig. 7 presents the CO emissions as a function of the residual oxygen content at the test points listed in Table 2.

A reduction in excess oxygen similarly leads to an increase in CO emissions, which is exponential within the near-stoichiometric range.

Table 4

95 % confidence interval of the CO emissions shown in Fig. 6 (in mg/MJ) for selected residual oxygen contents of the individual test series V1.1 to V1.5

Residual O ₂ in vol%	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.8	1.2
CI ₉₅ V1.1 in mg/MJ	313–363	118–170	37–45	7–9	4–5
CI ₉₅ V1.2 in mg/MJ	125–158	57–63	26–32	5–6	2–3
CI ₉₅ V1.3 in mg/MJ	168–220	83–100	35–39	7–8	4–5
CI ₉₅ V1.4 in mg/MJ	288–360	151–188	53–63	15–16	6–7
CI ₉₅ V1.5 in mg/MJ	426–557	185–242	100–123	24–25	11–12

Consequently, the ordinate (CO in mg/MJ) was also displayed logarithmically in this instance. A closer examination of the slightly over-stoichiometric range between 0.6 and 2.0 vol% residual oxygen reveals that CO emissions decrease with increasing amounts of injected water at each corresponding level of residual oxygen. It can be observed that the CO emissions at test point 2.2.1 are lower than those at test point 2.2.2, where the same amount of flue gas is recirculated but more water, 12.9 kg/h instead of 6.2 kg/h, is injected. This trend persists in the near-stoichiometric range from 0 to 0.6 vol% residual oxygen.

For test series II as well, error bars are omitted for better clarity, and instead the 95 % confidence interval is presented in tabular form in Table 5.

4. Simulation results

The results of the simulations are presented in Chapter 4. These include the flow field, the temperature distribution, the reaction rate of the reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ and the molar concentration of CO_2 in both simulated cases with and without water injection. To effectively visualize the reaction zone in both simulated scenarios and to illustrate the regions where CO is either produced or consumed, the net reaction rate of CO, the heat release field, as well as the molar concentrations of OH radicals and CH_2O are also presented. Fig. 8 illustrates the velocity field and the flow path lines with and without water injection in the axial section. To clarify the position of the section, a conceptual drawing of the combustion chamber is depicted on the right-hand side of Fig. 8. The section passes directly through one of the three points where liquid water is injected. Both flow fields exhibit a very similar pattern. As is typical for MILD combustion, there is a pronounced internal recirculation caused by the high velocity of the oxidizer at the inlet to the combustion chamber. The maximum velocity in the case with water injection is 121.1 m/s, while in the case without water injection, it is 121.8 m/s. Additionally, it can be observed that there is a slight indentation in the path lines when water injection is employed.

The temperature distribution for the two simulated cases is illustrated in Fig. 9. It is evident that the combustion chamber temperature is significantly lower when water injection is employed compared to the case without water injection. The maximum temperature recorded in the simulated case without water injection is 1878 K, which exceeds the heat resistance of the materials used for the combustion chamber and burner. In the simulation with water injection, a maximum temperature of 1480 K is obtained. In the absence of water injection, a typical, highly homogeneous temperature distribution within the combustion chamber is observed. However, in the case with water injection, this homogeneous distribution is primarily disrupted by the areas of liquid water injection. Nonetheless, temperature peaks, which are typically present in conventional combustion processes with flames, are not discernible.

The reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ is primarily responsible for the conversion of CO to CO_2 along the pathway $\text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$ [27]. The kinetic rate of this reaction is illustrated for both simulated cases in Fig. 10, presented in both the axial section through the combustion chamber and the radial section at the level of the water injection. The plotted quantity is the CO consumption (burnout) or formation with respect to the elementary step $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$, i.e. positive values indicate CO consumption (burnout) and negative values indicate CO formation through reaction of CO_2 with H radicals. In the case with water injection, the kinetic rate of reaction is highest directly at the points where water is injected (see Fig. 10b). Without water

injection, the reaction rate of the equilibrium reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ is shifted significantly to the left across nearly the entire chamber. Additionally, it is apparent that the reaction zone is considerably longer and more extensive in the scenario with water injection. Upon comparing the scaling of the legends across the axial sections displayed, it is evident that the reaction rate increases throughout the entire combustion chamber.

To demonstrate the effect of water injection on CO burnout and CO_2 formation, the distribution of CO_2 in the combustion chamber is presented in terms of molar concentration. Fig. 11a and b illustrate that the molar concentration of CO_2 is slightly higher at the points of water injection. It is important to note the differing scaling between Fig. 11a and b. The scaling in Fig. 11b is selected specifically to highlight the impact of water injection. An elevated molar concentration of CO_2 is also observed within the reaction zone in Fig. 11a. In contrast, the simulated case without water injection, depicted in Fig. 11c and d, reveals a very homogeneous distribution of CO_2 within the combustion chamber.

The net reaction rate of CO, i.e. the overall consumption or formation of CO resulting from all reactions of the mechanism and the heat release field presented in Fig. 12 indicate that the reaction zone is significantly broadened and enlarged in the combustion process with water injection compared to the combustion process without water injection. As is typical for a MILD combustion process, the heat release is not concentrated in a flame close to the burner head. Instead, the heat release is distributed over a large volume within the combustion chamber, which results in a homogeneous temperature distribution. The heat output in the case without water injection is concentrated in a considerably smaller area than in the case with water injection. Additionally, a region where the consumption of CO and the release of heat are intensified is observed immediately behind the water injection, while the release of heat is reduced directly at the point where water is injected. MILD combustion is predicated on a self-ignition process, initiated by the formation of CH_2O . Subsequently, the presence of OH radicals indicates the further progression of combustion reactions. The molar concentrations of OH radicals and CH_2O presented in Fig. 13 illustrate that the reaction zone occupies a larger volume as water injection is applied. Furthermore, it is observed that the concentration of OH radicals decrease in the immediate vicinity of the water injection, while the concentration of CH_2O shows a slight increase in this region.

For a better interpretation of the distribution of OH radicals in the case of water injection, which is shown in Fig. 13, the net reaction rate of OH radicals is also presented in Fig. 14. In order to clarify the impact of water injection and to identify where the majority of OH radicals are consumed, the scale in the axial section was adjusted accordingly, with a maximum value of $0 \text{ kg/m}^3 \text{ s}$ for this illustration. It can be observed in both the axial and radial sections that the net reaction rate of OH radicals in the water injection region has shifted significantly into the negative, indicating that OH radicals are being consumed at this location.

5. Discussion

The results generated are discussed in this section, with the numerical results serving to better understand and elucidate the experimental results. The accuracy of the measurement results is discussed first. During the test operation, the amount of oxygen supplied, starting from a residual oxygen content of approx. 2 vol%, is continuously reduced in small steps (approx. every 10 min) until no more oxygen can be measured in the flue gas. It is important to note that the residual oxygen content in the flue gas does not remain constant while a steady supply of pure oxygen is maintained. Rather, the measured residual oxygen content, just like the associated CO emissions, fluctuates around an average value. As a result, several (approx. 5–20) corresponding measured values of CO emissions are available for one residual oxygen content value. Each data point in Figs. 6 and 7 is the average of these several measured values. The individual measured values for CO emissions

Table 5

95 % confidence interval of the CO emissions shown in Fig. 6 (in mg/MJ) for selected residual oxygen contents of the individual test series V2.2.1 and V2.2.2

Residual O_2 in vol%	0.1	0.26	0.5	0.8	1.2
Cl_{95} V2.2.1 in mg/MJ	208–260	92–126	31–37	13–15	5–6
Cl_{95} V2.2.2 in mg/MJ	351–401	158–194	45–50	21–22	9–10

Fig. 8. Velocity field and flow structure within the combustion chamber for the simulated case with water injection (a). The location of the water injection is indicated by the red arrow. Panel (b) illustrates the velocity distribution and flow structure for the simulated case without water injection. To enhance comprehension of the axial section's position within the combustion chamber, a conceptual drawing of the combustion chamber, with the section highlighted in grey, is shown on the right. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Temperature distribution within the combustion chamber with water injection (a) and without water injection (b). The position of the axial section in the combustion chamber is identical with the one in Fig. 8.

Fig. 10. Representation of the kinetic rate of reaction of the reaction $CO + OH \rightleftharpoons CO_2 + H$. a) and b) show the field of the reaction rate in the axial and radial section in the simulated case with water injection. c) and d) refer to the case without water injection. The grey dotted line in the axial sections indicates the position of the radial section.

Fig. 11. Molar concentration of CO_2 inside the combustion chamber for the simulated case with water injection in axial section a) and radial section b) as well as for the case without water injection in axial section c) and radial section d). The grey dotted line in the axial sections a) and c) indicates the position of the radial sections.

Fig. 12. Net Reaction Rate of CO and field of Heat Release in the axial section of the combustion chamber for the simulated case with water injection a) and b) and for the case without water injection c) and d).

Fig. 13. Molar Concentration of OH radicals and CH₂O in the axial section of the combustion chamber for the simulated case with water injection a) and b) and for the case without water injection.

fluctuate around the mean value to varying degrees. The CO emissions fluctuate more strongly the closer it gets to stoichiometric operation ($\varphi = 1$). For test series V1.3, the fluctuation is as shown in Table 6.

In the case of a few specific residual oxygen levels, only very few or a single measurement point was recorded, which results in that point not fitting neatly into the curve. This is how individual outliers in the

Fig. 14. Net Reaction Rate of OH inside the combustion chamber for the simulated case with water injection in axial section a) and radial section b) at the height of water injection. The grey dotted line in the axial section a) indicates the position of the radial section.

Table 6

Fluctuation of the measured CO emissions at different associated residual oxygen contents.

O ₂ in vol%	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.8	1.2
CO _{min} in mg/MJ	138	65	31	7.8	4.86
CO _{max} in mg/MJ	382	118	51	8.6	4.28
CO _{mean} in mg/MJ	194	92	37	8	4.56

measurement results from Figs. 6 and 7 can be explained. It therefore means that these are of a statistical nature.

Both experimental results and simulation outcomes demonstrate the influence of water injection on various parameters characteristic of combustion processes. The simulations were not conducted to validate them against experimental results. Instead, the primary objective was to gain insights into the combustion chamber dynamics and to examine the effects of water injection on reaction progression and carbon monoxide formation. Furthermore, the CO emissions in the experimental studies are measured after the condenser, in the cold, carbon-capture-ready flue gas. In contrast, the simulations focus exclusively on the processes occurring within the combustion chamber.

The experimental work indicates that changes in CO emissions, associated with an increased CO₂ concentration in the combustion chamber due to a high rate of recirculated flue gas are also measurable in the cold, carbon-capture-ready flue gas. Furthermore, this effect can be mitigated by introducing liquid water directly into the combustion chamber, as this approach decreases the amount of CO₂ in the combustion chamber and replaces it with H₂O. The observed trend of decreasing CO emissions in the experiments of test series I (Table 1) with an increasing proportion of injected water and a decreasing proportion of recirculated, CO₂-rich flue gas can be attributed to the influence of H₂O on the combustion process at a chemical level. The competitive interaction between CO₂ and O₂ for H radicals is counteracted by water injection. This is evidenced by the altered reaction rate shown in Fig. 10, which results from water injection. It is clear that shifting the equilibrium of the CO + OH ⇌ CO₂ + H reaction to the right through water injection enhances CO burnout, which is further corroborated by Fig. 11. In this figure, an increase in the molar concentration of CO₂ is observed in the same regions where the kinetic reaction rate of the CO + OH ⇌ CO₂ + H reaction is shifted to the right. Additionally, H₂O serves as a source of OH radicals via the reaction O + H₂O ⇌ 2OH, supplying the necessary radicals for CO oxidation [28]. The decrease in OH radicals in Fig. 13b) can be attributed to the heightened consumption of these radicals in the water injection zone, as illustrated in Fig. 14. This elevated consumption can, in turn, be explained by the enhanced reaction rate presented in Fig. 10. The noticeably smaller reaction zone in the simulated case without water injection compared to the simulation

with water injection, which is shown in Figs. 12 and 13, is due to the significantly higher temperature in the combustion chamber. As the temperature level is fundamentally higher without water injection, the combustion reactions take place much faster and thus the heat release is concentrated to a smaller volume.

The residence time for test points V1.1 to V1.5 ranges from 1.7 s to 1.2 s, while the characteristic timescale of the chemical reactions is approximately 0.2–0.3 s. Therefore, it can be assumed that chemical equilibrium is reached at the outlet of the recuperative burner.

Furthermore, the hypothesis that a longer residence time, resulting from a reduced inflow of recirculated flue gas, suppresses CO emissions in measurement series I is contradicted by the experimental results from measurement series II. In measurement series II, the volume flow of recirculated flue gas remains constant while only the amount of injected water is varied, resulting in slightly lower residence time in case of higher water injection rate. Nevertheless, lower CO emissions are also recorded here with an increasing proportion of injected water in the cold, carbon-capture-ready flue gas. The measurable difference in CO emissions between operating points V2.2.1 and V2.2.2, averaged over all residual oxygen contents, is approximately –40 %. It is unlikely that the temperature influences CO emissions due to CO₂ dissociation in the results of measurement series II (Fig. 7). In all instances, the temperature remains below 1500 °C, above which dissociation effects become significant. The temperature distribution in the combustion chamber with water injection, as shown in Fig. 9, indicates that no temperature peaks exceed this threshold.

The disproportionate increase in CO emissions in the near-stoichiometric range of V1.1 cannot be conclusively explained with the available results. However, it is evident that with a very high quantity of injected water, the local temperature drops sharply. This scenario, combined with very low O₂ availability, leads to a more pronounced rise in CO emissions in this operating state. Both the homogeneous temperature distribution typical for MILD combustion and the high internal recirculation remain unaffected, provided that the amount of injected water is not excessive. Moreover, water injection allows for a reduction in combustion chamber temperature to a level suitable for the materials commonly used. It is demonstrated that water injection is an effective and feasible method for controlling combustion chamber temperature.

Regarding applicability to real systems, it appears that the direct injection of liquid water into the combustion chamber is a practical alternative to adding water vapor to the oxidizer or employing moist recirculation. In scenarios involving moist recirculation or the addition of water vapor to the oxidizer, the supply lines from the oxidizer to the burner typically require costly insulation or heating. Moreover, standard burner valves and burners may not be compatible. In contrast, the water injection method utilized here does not necessitate such measures,

allowing for the use of standard materials throughout.

6. Conclusion

This study examines the impact of water injection on the characteristics and CO formation of oxyfuel combustion of a low-calorific gaseous fuel. The objective is to determine if the effects are measurable in the cold flue gas and whether they are significant for oxyfuel combustion in the context of carbon capture. To achieve this, experimental work was conducted on a 50 kW pilot plant designed for the oxyfuel combustion of various gaseous fuels. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) modeling was employed to gain a deeper understanding of the experimental results. The key findings are summarized as follows:

CO emissions decrease with an increasing proportion of injected water and a decreasing proportion of recirculated, CO₂-rich flue gas. Only in the near-stoichiometric range is a more pronounced formation of CO emissions observed with a very high amount of injected water.

Additionally, a reduction in CO emissions is evident even when the amount of recirculated flue gas remains constant while the injected water increases.

This trend can be attributed to the influence of H₂O on the combustion process at a chemical level. Specifically, replacing CO₂ with H₂O changes the pool of OH radicals and diminishes the effect of the reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$, the equilibrium of which is typically shifted to the left during oxyfuel combustion due to the high concentration of CO₂ in the combustion process. This effect on CO emissions is measurable in the cold, carbon capture-ready flue gas. Therefore, it is determined that water injection has a beneficial impact on subsequent carbon capture applications.

The combustion chamber temperature in MILD combustion can be effectively and precisely controlled through liquid water injection. This method serves as a practical solution for moderating temperature. Moreover, injecting water directly into the combustion chamber is more straightforward than using wet recirculation when aiming to introduce specific amounts of H₂O. Furthermore, there is no disturbance to the homogeneous temperature distribution as long as the localized quantity of injected water is not excessive. This issue could be addressed by increasing the number of injection points, which would reduce the localized water injection amount and, consequently, the temperature drop.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Felix Lehner: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christian Groves:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Martin Meiller:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Slawomir Sladek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Philipp Schlatter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Formal analysis.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used FhGenie in order to translate the text from German into English and to ensure better readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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